

Summary Report on Paradise Island Submersed Aquatic Vegetation

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by
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INTRODUCTION

This report was prepared at the request of the Lake Pontchartrain Basin Foundation to provide information about the distribution and abundance of submersed aquatic vegetation (SAV) in the vicinity of Paradise Island located in St. Tammany Parish, LA. Although personnel conducting this survey have conducted annual surveys of SAV distribution in Lake Pontchartrain, these surveys did not include canals associated with the adjacent marsh. Field work was conducted by J. Cho and James Sinclair who have conducted similar field studies through the University of New Orleans. Their work was supervised by Dr. Michael A. Poirrier, a research professor at the University of New Orleans.

MATERIALS and METHODS

The canal surrounding Paradise Island (30.23596183637847, -89.85397196395293) was surveyed on Nov 2, 2001 to determine occurrence of SAV, species present, relative abundance and areal cover. Paradise Island is located northeast of Lake Pontchartrain in Slidell (map attached; Fig. 1). Rooted plants were examined and identified by observing through a viewing box and collecting plants by raking the bottom of the area while cruising with a boat. The boat was driven in a grid-like search pattern over the entire area of the old boat harbor on the south side of Paradise Island. The shore of the island and the opposite shore across the canal were surveyed around the entire perimeter of the island. Samples of each SAV species collected were preserved in 10% formalin solution.

RESULTS

The list of the species found follows:

Najas guadalupensis (Southern Naiad)
Ruppia maritima (Widgeon Grass)
Vallisneria americana (Wild Celery)
Eleocharis parvula (Dwarf Spikerush)
Zannichellia palustris (Horned Pondweed)
Myriophyllum spicatum (Eurasian Milfoil)

Najas guadalupensis was most abundant. It occurred continuously as a bottom carpet from the shores to a water depth of 4-5 ft. *Ruppia maritima* and *Myriophyllum*

spicatum were present throughout the canal. *Ruppia* was abundant along the north side of the Island. *Eleocharis parvula* occurred sporadically along the shore at the intertidal zone. *Zannichellia palustris* was found occasionally during this survey, especially in the old boat harbor. *Vallisneria americana* was also present, the blades were healthy and dense. The distribution of SAV is shown on the attached map. Generally, SAV covered the area between the shore to a water depth of about 4 ft.

DISCUSSION

Submersed aquatic vegetation plays several critical ecological roles. Grassbeds are major food sources for waterfowl, fish and other aquatic invertebrates (Cottam 1939), including crabs and shrimps. They also serve as critical nursery areas for larvae and juveniles of estuarine organisms (Orth *et al.* 1984). Their roots and rhizomes help to stabilize sediments (Ginsburg and Lowenstam 1958) and their above-ground vegetative shoots help to reduce shoreline erosion by buffering wave energy (Orth 1977, Ward *et al.* 1984). Also, oxygen is produced as a byproduct of SAV photosynthesis (Hartman and Brown 1966, Moeslund *et al.* 1981). Moreover, they assimilate excess plant nutrients (Mickle and Wetzel 1978, 1979) and remove some pollutants from the water column (Ray and White 1976, Fayed *et al.*, 1985, Mortimer 1985). Grassbeds (SAV) are one of the vital elements in EFH (essential fish habitat) that is defined by the National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) as “waters and substrate necessary to fish for spawning, breeding, feeding, or growth to maturity”. Therefore, SAV decline in Lake Pontchartrain (Burns *et al.* 1993, Cho 1998) and in surrounding aquatic habitats can have serious affects on fisheries (blue crabs, shrimps and other fin fish that are recreationally and commercially important) as well as on the entire aquatic ecosystem.

The Paradise Island Canal supports diverse SAV and it may serve as an SAV source habitat to Lake Pontchartrain (Fig. 2). Recently, Lake Pontchartrain has lost several freshwater SAV species that were present before 1998 (Cho and Poirrier 2000). *Najas*, *Eleocharis*, *Zannichellia*, and *Potamogeton perfoliatus* do no longer exist in the Lake. Once the most abundant species in the Lake, *Vallisneria americana*, also has been in a state of decline and its abundance decreased significantly during the high salinity period in 1999 to 2000 (Cho and Poirrier 2001). Although, the high salinity and clear water in 1999 and 2000 resulted in a dramatic increase of *Ruppia* in the Lake, its future status is not predictable as the salinity and turbidity of the Lake returns to the historic average.

Canals and Bayous adjacent to Lake Pontchartrain are critical sources for SAV that have been lost from the Lake. The 1999 *Ruppia* increase in the Lake was partially caused by the seeds or seedling dispersion from these streams and surrounding ponds during the 1998 hurricanes and tropical storms (Cho and Poirrier 2001). *Vallisneria* began to recover in the Lake in the summer of 2001 after the years of continual decrease. These *Vallisneria* recoveries were also initially observed near the north shore streams (personal observations of UNO biologists during the 2001 SAV surveys). In order to maintain healthy ecosystems and rich aquatic resources, healthy and diverse SAV populations should be protected. Destroying SAV source habitats such as the Paradise Island area will inhibit recolonization of the favorable indigenous freshwater species (*Vallisneria*, *Najas*, *Zannichellia* and *Eleocharis*) into Lake Pontchartrain.

Dredging of the proposed site will directly destroy not only SAV, but also many organisms that depend on SAV. Impacts of dredging on SAV are persistent (Bell 1993) because it eliminates below-ground roots, rhizomes and seed reserves. Surrounding marsh will be affected also, because aquatic plants typically occur as a continuum of submersed, inter-tidal low marsh and high marsh types. Destruction of any of these plant types causes disturbance in the system. Although, an invasive species, *Myriophyllum spicatum* does occur around Paradise Island, this species has not caused noxious problems such as formation of surface canopies in that area. Dredging will result in loss of favorable SAV (*Vallisneria*, *Ruppia*, *Najas*, *Eleocharis*, *Zannichellia* and possibly other *Potamogeton* sp.) and other valuable aquatic resources rather than eradicating an invasive species.

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Modified map from Maps On Us

Figure 1. Survey location, Paradise Island, is located in Slidell, Louisiana.

Figure 2. Species and locations of submersed aquatic vegetation (SAV) documented in Paradise Island, Slidell, Louisiana.